

A predictor of the rates of clinical events — a general research direction —

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1 Introduction

Any treatment decision requires estimating the risks of various options for a specific patient.

While this risk estimation seems relatively simple for short-term effects of acute diseases in otherwise healthy young people, especially if they have a known, external cause, such as a germ or trauma, it is almost impossible to perform correctly for longer term predictions in older patients with multiple chronic pathologies and treatments.

The complexity of risk estimation quickly increases when genomic and other modern investigation data are taken into account and easily overcomes the ability of the individual physician without computational support.

In other terms, if one has an acute, immediately life-threatening disease, this is obviously his major risk of death or major complications and treatments addressing this acute disease are the best options to reduce this risk; however, if one has a number of conditions and undergoes various treatments, but is not in an immediate danger, it is not currently possible to actually calculate the probabilities causes of death, or serious clinical events, over months or years and demonstrate the soundness of the calculation method.

Without a sound, reproducible, base for risk estimation, the rationale of choosing between treatment options frequently remains disputable.

This intrinsically hard problem may hypothetically be one of the reasons why, despite continuous increase in health spending and health research investments, we observe a capping of the life expectancy increase and diminishing returns on investment.

An example of the general problem: a 60 year old male with 10 years old controlled diabetes (average HbA1C=7%) and fatty liver disease, without complications, is treated daily with Metformin 2000mg, Rosuvastatin 20mg, Aspirin 75mg. Calculate his risk of death over the next 5 years, for each probable cause. How does this risk profile change if he stops taking Aspirin? Show the theoretical and experimental basis of the calculation.

Such problems cannot be solved, and solutions cannot be verified, directly, based on observed event rates in sufficient samples of similar patients because, as the number of variables increases, the similar population becomes vanishingly smaller—a phenomenon we call the sample fragmentation problem.

1.1 Purpose of this document

This document describes the general research direction addressing the problem of treatment risk estimation in chronic non-communicable diseases. Here, a ‘general research direction’ means a broad objective that is sought by numerous efforts across the world. Efforts occur in many fields, from mathematics to bioinformatics to biological and clinical research, that could be seen as contributing to such a solution in various formulations of the problem.

In this introduction, we review the various issues that arise in efforts towards a general clinical predictor and try to identify approaches and milestones that could help disparate groups and projects to avoid parallelisms and achieve synergies.

1.2 Aim of the research direction

The aim of the general clinical predictor could be formulated as the development of a computer program, named here ‘PREDICL’, that takes as inputs (1) the history of the patient, including investigation data and previous treatments and (2) various management options; and produces as output

(a) estimations the rates of future clinical events in time, for each management option and (b) a step by step explanation of how these estimates were obtained and the primary data that were used.

This is a deep tech problem that cannot be solved in the general case and for all the available data.

It can be solved to a useful extent for some specific cases from the simpler problems mentioned above. However, in all patient subgroups, treatment failures and secondary effects will occur, that could be reduced with improved prediction—for example, by taking supplementary variables into account, in particular genetic variables. Thus, even for simpler problems, regarding the evolution of acute events, models including more variables could provide an improvement, but they cannot be developed directly, by sampling populations, because of the sample fragmentation problem.

1.3 Subproblems and subdirections

In this section we attempt a decomposition of the general problem. The development of any clinical prediction method has a more or less developed solution to each component. Achieving a more general prediction method, however, requires standardisation and combination of these approaches, as well as substantial theoretical development.

1.3.1 Components of the PREDICL tool

1. data description language (named SOLON below)—a formal, computer processable, unified language and ontology is needed, that describes: (1) disease classifications and parameters; (2) pathophysiologic and investigation parameters, including genomic parameters; (3) treatments; (4) clinical events; (5) predictive models of some parameters and events from others; (6) systematic observations and experiments that resulted in the predictive models as well as protocols; (6) regulations such as treatment algorithms or clinical guideline recommendations; (7) uncertainty in all of the above; (8) references to sources; (9) clinical cases.
2. a potentially distributed knowledge base of SOLON statements that reflects the contents of the literature, associated datasets and cases, named SOLBASE;

3. a search engine, named PREDICL that, given a case description, extracts statements from the solon database that are relevant to that case and, based on these, applies predictive models and inferences producing probabilistic predictions.

1.3.2 Validation of the PREDICL tool

A method and tools for validation of PREDICL predictions, once the actual evolution of each case is known and recorded, need to be developed.

Individual predictions cannot be validated, in principle, because all predictions are probabilistic. Specific stochastic models and methods need to be developed to evaluate the accuracy of these probabilities on population samples.

1.3.3 Datasets and models on which PREDICL is based

The development of the SOLBASE knowledge base is the most complex part of the project and involves at least the following activities:

1. the extraction of data and predictive models from previous studies and uniform representation as solon structures;
2. development of potentially simpler observational and experimental types studies that do not each, by themselves, result in definitive predictors of major events, but can contribute to the improvement of the broader models mentioned above, for example by measuring rates involved in pathological state transitions;
3. development and integration of population pathophysiologic and pharmacogenomic models that describe the relationship between genes, laboratory measurements, drug regimens and other measurables with patient evolution;
4. the theoretical development of methods of combining more specific models, that predict incremental evolution events, such as the occurrence of an ECG abnormality, into broader models that predict important endpoints such as mortality or major morbidity (like a life-threatening arrhythmia) and their complications; the broader models are typically stochastic kinetic models in a multidimensional state space of patient profiles.

1.3.4 Deployment in clinical practice

Clinical application of PREDICL requires the introduction of a new profession that involves the introduction and validation of individual patient data, invocation of relevant models and the management of predictive results. Using PREDICL will involve peculiar technical abilities that are not common among physicians, but also familiarity with medical and biological terminology. It will also require the dedication of substantial time that is not available to most practicing physicians.

Certification and approval of PREDICL and associated tools by medical device authorities is also an activity that is classified here. It involves a continuous process as successive versions and possibly different variants of PREDICL are released.

PREDICL will not be necessary or useful in many situations where current practice is adequate, in particular in acute conditions in otherwise healthy individuals. Identifying the circumstances where the PREDICL approach would be needed, in particular cases, will in itself be a clinical practice issue, that will depend on the continuously evolving capabilities of PREDICL systems.

1.3.5 Technical developments

Software development will involve:

1. implementation of the SOLON language and SOLBASE knowledge base;
2. simulator and other model implementations;
3. design and development of user interfaces;
4. development of interfaces with other software systems that manage various datasets, including patient data.

Other activities must seek the development of procedures and diagnostic and treatment algorithms involving PREDICL.

1.3.6 Research policy models

The state of the art, feasibility, cost and planning of predictive methods available or that could be developed need to be explored for each specific category and reported in a standardised form.

An econometric model for prioritisation of projects aiming to include new models in PREDICL could be developed. It needs to take into account existing human resources, the rate of formation of new human resources, available datasets and the general progress of dataset generation and financial resources.